

COMPATIBILITY OF Si-C-O FIBER AND Si-C FIBER WITH ALUMINUM

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SUMMARY: Two kinds of SiC-based fibers have been evaluated for their compatibility with aluminum. Si-C-O (Nicalon) fiber and oxygen-free cured Si-C (Hi-Nicalon) fiber were coated with pure aluminum and heat treated at 700°C for different times. Tensile test of Al-coated fibers showed that Si-C fiber had lower strength degradation than Si-C-O fiber. DSC thermogram displayed an exothermic peak as a proof of interface reaction between Si-C-O fiber and aluminum. SEM and TEM observation of SiC/Al composites exhibited that Si-C-O fiber reacted with aluminum more readily than Si-C fiber. Two kinds of SiC-based fiber reinforced aluminum composite wires were prepared by ultrasonic liquid infiltration method. After exposed at the temperature lower than 500°C for 30min the wire strength reduction was less than 10%. If heated at 600 °C and 700°C, Si-C-O/Al wire lost its half strength and was near to zero, respectively. But for Si-C/Al wire, strength degradation was 20% (600°C-30 min heating) and 88% (700°C-30 min heating). Low-oxygen Si-C fiber has been improved in compatibility with aluminum.

KEYWORDS: SiC fiber, aluminum matrix composites, physical vapor deposition, squeeze casting, ultrasonic liquid infiltration, tensile strength, scanning electron microscopy, transmission electron microscopy.

INTRODUCTION

SiC particles, whiskers and fibers are extensively used for reinforcing aluminum matrix composites. This is because SiC is the most stable thermodynamically for SiC-Al interface, comparing to the other reinforcements of aluminum composites, such as carbon, alumina, potassium titanate and so on. It has taken almost 25 years since Yajima *et al* [1] invented the method to prepare coreless SiC-based fibers. The preparation of the fibers involve the spinning of molten polycarbosilane(PCS), the curing of the green PCS fibers in an oxidizing atmosphere and pyrolysis in an inert atmosphere. Such fibers are commercially available under the trade name Nicalon and Tyranno, respectively. The former is Si-C-O fiber and the latter belongs to Si-Ti-C-O fiber. These SiC-based fibers have been used to reinforce

aluminum composites. Many studies have shown that it is necessary to control fiber-Al contact time at high temperature in order to prepare SiC/Al composites with excellent properties. This is because such SiC-based fibers also react with aluminum matrix. The principal reaction between Si-C-O or Si-Ti-C-O fibers and aluminum is one of SiO_xC_y phase in the fibers with aluminum during fabricating SiC/Al composites. Generally, Si-C-O or Si-Ti-C-O fibers are cured in an oxygen atmosphere before being sintered to ceramic fibers and there exist 11-18wt% oxygen content in the fibers [1,2]. Elimination of SiC-Al interfacial reaction is expected if low oxygen fibers are available. Fortunately, according to an electron beam irradiation curing process, SiC-based fibers having a very low oxygen content (≤ 0.5 wt%), have been developed. These fibers are supplied as spools of continuous yarns under trade name Hi-Nicalon [3,4].

The aim of the present work is to evaluate the compatibility of Nicalon (Si-C-O) and Hi-Nicalon (Si-C) fibers with aluminum, by characterizing the tensile strength of Al-coated fibers after heating at high temperature. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) has also been used as thermal analysis to explain the chemical reaction behavior of the two fibers with aluminum. In addition, these fibers reinforced aluminum composite wires have been prepared by an ultrasonic liquid infiltration method and compared in their tensile strength after thermal exposure in different temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Materials

Si-C-O (Nicalon) and Si-C (Hi-Nicalon) fibers were supplied by Nippon Carbon Co., Ltd., Japan. The chemical composition of the as-received fibers is shown in Table 1. The oxygen

Table 1: Chemical composition of Si-C-O and Si-C fibers

	wt%				atomic ratio			
	Si	C	O	H	Si	C	O	H
Si-C-O (Nicalon)	59.0	30.0	11.0	--	1.00	1.19	0.33	0.05
Si-C (Hi-Nicalon)	63.7	35.8	0.5	--	1.00	1.31	0.01	0.1

content of Si-C-O fiber is very high (11 wt%) with respect to the oxygen-free cured fibers Si-C (0.5 wt%). The C:Si atomic ratio is 1.19 for Si-C-O fiber and 1.31 for Si-C fiber, respectively. It means that the two kinds of fibers contain free carbon. The fibers are received in the form of tows of approximately 500 filaments and a spool of continuous fibers coated with polyvinyl acetate (PVA) sizing is provided. The PVA sizing of the as-received fibers was removed by heating at 450°C for 30 min in air. Pure aluminum (Al/99.99 wt%) was used as the matrix of SiC/Al composites.

Heat Treatment and Tensile Test of Al-coated SiC Fibers

PVA sizing-removed SiC fibers were set in a vacuum physical vapor deposition (PVD) device to coat aluminum on the fibers. By this method, 0.7-2.3 μm thick aluminum layer was deposited on the fibers. Al-coated SiC fibers were re-heated at 700°C for 0.5-30 min in air to investigate mechanical property of the fibers after thermal exposure. Heat-treated SiC fibers

were immersed in 15% HCl aqueous solution for 5h to dissolve the residual aluminum on the fibers.

The monofilament tensile test of the heat-treated SiC fibers was done at room temperature with a tensile machine (TENSILON/STM-T-50BP). Test piece was prepared according to Japanese Industrial Standard (JIS R7601). A batch of about 30 monofilaments was tested for every treatment condition using a gauge length of $L=10$ mm and tensile speed of 0.2mm/min. Tensile strength was calculated by the fracture load and the fiber diameter. The latter was the average value of three data measured using a laser dia-measuring device.

The morphology of the fiber surface was observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to compare the compatibility of the two kinds of SiC fibers with aluminum, using a Hitachi S-800H microscope.

Squeeze Cast and Interface Analysis of SiC/Al Composites

Si-C-O fibers and Si-C fibers were piled up to be a preform, pre-heated to 450°C and then set into a metal mold, respectively. Pure aluminum melt of 780°C was poured in the mold. Meanwhile, a ram was driven down and the liquid aluminum was squeezed into the fiber preform. Aluminum solidified under 100MPa pressure. The part of preform became fiber/Al composites.

Thermal analysis was carried out by differential scanning calorimetry apparatus (Rigaku DSC-8270A). Standard specimen and crucible were high purity α -Al₂O₃. The heating was in high pure Ar atmosphere (flow 100ml/min) from room temperature to 1000°C. Interface microstructure was observed using a TOPCON EM-002B transmission electron microscope equipped with EDX device. The samples were cut from the SiC/Al composites after heated at 700°C for 30min in vacuum. SiC fibers were extracted from the same composites by dissolving aluminum matrix in 15% HCl aqueous solution. Composition analysis of the fiber surface was performed with an electron probe micro analyzer (JOEL JXA-8900RL).

Preparation and Tensile Strength of SiC/Al Composite Wires

Si-C-O fiber and Si-C fiber reinforced pure aluminum composite wires were prepared by an ultrasonic liquid infiltration method [5]. A tow of fibers passes through a crucible containing molten aluminum (about 680°C), a high intensity ultrasound (500 W, 18 kHz) was delivered to the molten aluminum by a horn and consequently exerted a high intensive ultrasonic field around the individual fiber. Under the action of ultrasound, aluminum melt infiltrated in the fibers. The fibers combined with aluminum to be a composite wire after being pulled out from the crucible. The diameter of a composite wire was about 0.5 mm. The contact time between SiC fiber and aluminum can be controlled to <1s and hence the detrimental interfacial reaction can be minimized. In order to compare mechanical property of SiC/Al composites, two kinds of composite wires were heat treated at the temperatures of 400, 500, 600 and 700°C for 30 min in air, respectively. Their tensile tests were carried out using an Autograph (Shimazu AG-G50kN). The test conditions were: tensile speed 2mm/min, specimen gauge length 50mm. Sample number was about ten for an average.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile Strength of Al-coated SiC Fibers after Thermal Exposure

Two kinds of Al-coated SiC fibers were heated in air at 700°C for different times. Their tensile strengths after thermal exposure are listed in Table 2. Tensile strengths of the as-received fibers are in the same level. Their diameters are equivalent too. The strength ratio of

the fiber after heating to the as-received fiber is drawn with the correspondent heating temperatures in

Table 2: Tensile strengths of Al-coated SiC fiber heated for different times

Heating Conditions	Si-C-O Fiber				Si-C Fiber			
	n	d _f (μm)	σ _f (GPa)	C.V(%)	n	d _f (μm)	σ _f (GPa)	C.V(%)
As-received	33	13.9	3.50	22.4	43	13.9	3.55	26.7
700•-0.5min	38	13.7	3.36	21.8	34	13.8	3.38	13.1
- 1 min	53	14.5	2.87	13.8	--	---	---	---
- 2 min	34	13.8	2.32	16.8	38	13.7	2.96	18.5
- 5 min	18	13.4	1.51	13.4	--	---	---	---
-10 min	30	13.5	1.40	17.1	33	14.2	2.68	16.7
-30 min	25	15.2	1.08	22.0	34	13.8	2.98	20.5

NOTE: n • sample number, d_f • average diameter of fiber, σ_f • average tensile strength of fiber, C.V • coefficient variation of fiber strength.

Fig. 1: Heating time dependence of Al-coated SiC fiber strength after thermal exposure.

Fig.1. If heating for just 30 s, two fiber strengths begin to decrease. Si-C-O fiber displays a faster reduction rate than Si-C fiber. If heating for 5min, Si-C-O fiber strength losses almost 60%. In the case of thermal exposure for 30min, its strength has only 30 % of the as-received fiber strength. It means that Si-C-O fiber has undergone a severe interfacial reaction with aluminum during thermal exposure. As for oxygen-free cured Si-C fiber, heating for 2min has made a strength degradation of about 20 %. To extend the heating time does not seem to decrease fiber strength further. The strength of the Si-C fiber after heated from 2min to 30min, can keep about 80 % strength of the as-received fibers.

(a) Si-C-O fiber: As-received

(b) Al-coated Si-C-O fiber: 700°C-30min

(c) Si-C fiber: As-received

(d) Al-coated Si-C fiber: 700°C-30min

Fig. 2: SEM images of Si-C-O fiber (a,b) and Si-C fiber (c,d) in the as-received state and after thermal exposure.

Fig.2 shows SEM micrographs of two kinds of SiC fibers. PVA sizing in the as-received fibers were removed by heating in air at 450°C for 40min. Al-coated fibers were heated at 700°C for 30 min and then immersed in 15% HCl for 5h to dissolve the possible residual aluminum, before SEM observation. As-received Si-C-O and Si-C fibers appear smooth and clean (Fig.2a, 2c). No any defects can be seen. But for heated Si-C-O fiber, the surface becomes uneven. So many small knobs and micro dimples (size 0.2-0.3 μm) have emerged from the fiber surface (Fig.2b). SiC fiber belongs to ceramic material and is very sensitive to the surface defects (crack, stress concentration and so on). Such convex and concave surface must lead the fiber strength to having a severe degradation. In the case of Si-C, there are not any visible changes for both the as-received fiber and the thermal exposed (Fig.2c, d).

Low-oxygen content is considered as a direct reason why Al-coated Si-C fiber can keep its strength in a high level after heated at 700°C for 30 min.

Interfacial Reaction between SiC Fiber and Aluminum

In the as-received state, Si-C fiber consists of \bullet -SiC crystals ranging in size from 2-15nm, as compared to 1-4nm for the Si-C-O fiber [6]. The higher value of density of Si-C fiber with respect to Si-C-O fiber (2.77gcm^{-3} and 2.56gcm^{-3} , respectively), can be assigned to the absence of oxygen containing substances (i.e., a low density material SiO_xC_y) and to the better crystalline state of both the SiC and free carbon phases [7]. Oxygen containing substances react with aluminum easily at high temperature. Fig.3 shows the DSC thermograms of two kinds of SiC/Al composites prepared by squeeze cast. The heating has been divided into two steps. One is heating at the rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ up to 600°C , another is at the rate of $3^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ from 600°C to 1000°C . The endothermic peaks indicate the melting of aluminum. In the thermogram of Si-C-O/Al composites, an exothermic peak begins at about 690°C (peak temperature 741.6°C), which reveals an interface reaction between Si-C-O fiber and aluminum. It is near to the temperature of thermal exposure on Al-coated fibers at which Si-C-O fiber strength reduces dramatically. But for Si-C/Al composites, there is not an apparent exothermic peak until about 800°C .

Fig. 3: DSC thermograms of SiC/Al composites.

Two kinds of SiC/Al composites were heated at 730°C for 30 min in vacuum. After heating the fibers were extracted from composites ingot. EPMA composition analysis results for the extracted fibers are listed in Table 3. It can be seen that both extracted fibers have a trace amount of aluminum. For Si-C-O fiber, there is little difference between the as-received fiber and the extracted fiber in oxygen content, whereas Si:C has an obvious reduction (from 0.40 to 0.28). It implies that some silicon in fiber surface has dissolved by the reaction and escaped out of the fiber. Oppositely, the composition of Si-C fiber in two states has little change. It has also proved that Si-C fiber is more stable than Si-C-O. The interface TEM micrographs of two kinds of SiC/Al composites after heated at 700°C for 30 min are shown in Fig.4. For both composites, there exists a dark zone in their interfaces. It should be the reaction layer of the fiber with aluminum.

The thickness is 0.79-0.98 μm (Si-C-O/Al) and 0.47 μm (Si-C/Al), respectively. EDX analysis results indicate that aluminum has diffused into the inside of the fiber.

Table 3: Composition of the as-received and extracted SiC fibers by EPMA (at %)

Elements	Si-C-O Fiber		Si-C Fiber	
	As-received	After heated	As-received	After heated
Si	24.5	19.2	23.1	24.0
C	62.0	68.6	73.4	72.1
O	13.5	12.1	3.5	3.9
Al	--	0.08	--	0.08

Fig. 4: TEM images and EDX spectra of Si-C-O/Al (left) and Si-C/Al (right) composites.

Aluminum has entered deeper for Si-C/Al than that of Si-C-O/Al composite. As a composition comparison in the matrix where leaves from the interface the same distance, ratio Si:Al of Si-C-O/Al is larger than that of Si-C/Al (see EDX spectra of d). Aluminum diffuses into the fiber, reacts with SiO_xC_y. Si or a Si-included product is created and enters into the matrix. If there are more SiO_xC_y compounds in fiber surface layer, as a result of reaction, plenty of silicon can be detected in the matrix side. Oppositely, aluminum enters in the fiber deeper.

Fabrication and Properties of SiC/Al Composite Wires

SiC-based fibers belong to ceramic and encounter two problems during fabrication of aluminum composites. One is the poor wettability between the fiber and liquid aluminum, which disables to fabricate SiC/Al composites by a common casting process. Another is the chemical reactivity between fiber and aluminum, which leads to fiber damage easily. In order to obtain SiC/Al composites with excellent properties, it becomes very important to control the interfacial reaction. High intensity ultrasound has been confirmed to be an appropriate means for preparation of aluminum matrix composites. When an ultrasonic energy is introduced into a liquid medium, a temporary negative pressure arises in some regions owing to the vortex flow and other physical effects. An induced excessive tensile stress creates many bubbles in the regions. These bubbles are in an unstable state and will oscillate under the action of ultrasound field. If the negative acoustic pressure exceeds a certain limitation, the bubbles expand rapidly and subsequently collapse or implode at a fast speed. While the bubbles collapse, a rather substantial compressive shock wave forms and propagates through the liquid. This behavior is called the cavitation effect of high intensity ultrasound. If cavitation happens, a shock wave can generate a powerful hydraulic pulse of 500-1000MPa or originate cumulative jets at a speed approximately 50-100m/s evaluated theoretically [8]. By such high pressure created in local area, liquid aluminum incorporates with the fibers to be a composite. There are a few examples to fabricate continuous fiber and particle reinforced aluminum matrix composites [9-11]. Two kinds of SiC-based fibers reinforced aluminum composite wires have been prepared by the ultrasonic liquid infiltration in the present work. Their properties can be seen from Table 4.

Table 4: Mechanical properties of SiC fibers and SiC/Al composite wires

Properties	Si-C-O		Si-C	
	Fiber	Wire	Fiber	Wire
Diameter (μm)	13.9	500	13.9	500
Number of Filaments	500	500	500	500
Density (g.cm ⁻³)	2.56	2.65	2.77	2.73
Tensile Strength (GPa)	3.50	1.16	3.55	1.28
• _{ROM} (GPa)	---	1.38	---	1.40
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	220	---	270	---
E _{ROM} (GPa)	---	125	---	144

NOTE: •_{ROM} and E_{ROM} are tensile strength and elastic modulus calculated by the rule of mixture (ROM), respectively. Volume fraction of the fiber in composite wires is 38.6 %.

Fig. 5 shows the photos of a composite wire. In a SiC/Al composite wire (diameter is about 0.5 mm), there are 500 filaments which are distributed among the aluminum matrix. Composite wire is characterized as having high tensile strength and high modulus.

This is because the fiber can be incorporated with aluminum in a short time (<1s), there is not enough time to enable the fiber damage due to interfacial reaction.

Composite wires can be fabricated to an available structural material by a few methods such as hot pressing, hot rolling, liquid metal dipping [12] and so on. Whichever fabrication method is used may involve SiC fiber contacting with aluminum matrix at an elevated temperature.

Fig. 5: SiC/Al composite wires prepared by the composite ultrasonic liquid infiltration method

(The photo wires after heated at different temperatures of top right is OM microstructure of a wire section).

Fig. 6: Tensile strength of SiC/Al for 30 min

It is important to ensure a stable interface between SiC fiber and aluminum matrix for a suitable fabrication process. Si-C/Al and Si-C-O/Al composite wires were re-heated from the room temperature to 400-700°C for 30 min in air. Their tensile strengths are shown in Fig.6. For the as-fabricated composite wires, tensile strength of Si-C/Al and Si-C-O/Al are 1283 MPa and 1155 MPa, respectively. After thermal exposure at 400°C, the strength of Si-C-O/Al wire degraded about 10 %, whereas Si-C/Al wire had not any change. Si-C/Al could keep its strength till 500°C heating. After heated at 600°C, the strength of Si-C/Al wire was 1061MPa(about 20 % loss). But for the same treatment Si-C-O/Al wire lost half strength. Furthermore, if heated at 700°C, Si-C-O/Al wire became too weak to support any load, whereas Si-C/Al wire had a strength of about 160 MPa. These results indicate that SiC/Al composite wires can be combined by the hot process at a temperature lower than 500°C below 30 min. If fabricated at an elevated temperature higher than 500°C, Si-C-O/Al will have more strength degradation than Si-C/Al composites.

CONCLUSIONS

1. During heating Al-coated fibers at 700°C for different times, Si-C fiber has shown a less strength reduction than that of Si-C-O fiber.
2. There exists not any exothermic peaks in DSC thermogram of Si-C/Al composites, whereas an exothermic peak has been found to begin at about 690• for Si-C-O/Al.
3. Comparing to Si-C-O/Al, Si-C/Al composite wires have a high tensile strength and low strength degradation after thermal exposure.
4. The compatibility between Si-C fiber and aluminum has been improved. The reason is that the low-oxygen in Si-C fiber is suitable for decreasing the reactivity of the fiber with aluminum.

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